

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

Sampling compartments and collectors

**Version 1
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Sampling compartments and collectors

A. Description

Samples compartments and collectors in FED-AMR project according to its design and aims.

B. Samples compartments and collectors

EU Region	Lead Collector 1	Lead collector 2	Samples available from Compartment										
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
East	Dr. Magdalena Zimova (MZ)	n.a	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	White	White
	Dr. Zdislava Bostikova (ZB)		White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White
North	Prof. Tanel Tenson (TT)	Dr. Solveig Sølverød Mo (SSM)	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	White
			White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	Purple
South	Dr. Manuela Caniça (MC)	Dr. Monica Oleastro (MO)	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
West	Dr. Adriana Cabal-Rosel (AC)	White	Cyan	Cyan	Cyan	Cyan	Cyan	Cyan	Cyan	Cyan	White	Cyan	Cyan
		White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	Yellow	Yellow
		Blue	Blue	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White

Compartment	Ecosystem
Compartment 1	Pig barn; farm, stable
Compartment 2	Manure (pig)
Compartment 3	Soil: agricultural fields
Compartment 4	Crop
Compartment 5	Field drainage
Compartment 6	Surface, river water
Compartment 7	Drinking water, ground
Compartment 8	Feed (crops; imported and/or locally cultivated)
Compartment 9	Farmers and associated personnel incl. family members
Compartment 10	Wastewater treatment plant
Compartment 11	Wild Animals